

Antiandrogenic effect and biological potency of some of the organogermanium(IV) complexes[†]

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Manuscript received 13 December 2011, accepted 10 February 2012

Abstract : An important study has been made in the search for the better fungicides, bactericides and antiandrogen agents on the organogermanium(IV) complexes of sulphonamide-imines. The complexes were screened *in vitro* against bacteria and fungi to test their antimicrobial property and *in vivo* on male albino rats to test their antifertility properties. The treatment with the sulphonamide-imines and their organogermanium complexes at the dose levels of 2 mg and 4 mg per day per rat did not cause any significant change in the body weight, but a significant reduction in the weights of reproductive organs was observed. Arrest of spermatogenesis was noted at various stages with the production of primary spermatocytes, secondary spermatocytes and step-19 spermatids found to be decreased. Biochemical parameters of tissues, i.e. protein, sialic acid, cholesterol, content of testes and seminal vesicular fructose also showed significant reduction. Further, the serum testosterone concentrations were also decreased after the treatment with the sulphonamide-imines and their organogermanium complexes.

Keywords : Antifertility, hematological studies, histopathological studies, sulphonamide-imines, tissue biochemistry, organogermanium compounds.

Introduction

In modern chemistry microwave synthesis represents one of the important dimensions. In inorganic chemistry, microwave technology has been used since the late 1970s, while it has only been implemented in organic chemistry since mid 1980s. Heating a chemical reactor by microwave radiation (just like in a microwave oven) has the advantage that it is rapid and the entire volume of the reactor is heated simultaneously, which can lead to less by-product and/or decomposition products. In this system, it is possible to rapidly increase the temperature for above the conventional boiling point of the solvent used¹. When we compare this unconventional energy source technology with classical heating we find that conventional heating process usually starts at the wall of the reactor due to this the core takes much longer time to achieve the target temperature. On the other hand the shorter reaction time and expanded reaction range offered by microwave-assisted synthesis with an advantage that it is cost effective and less equipment is required, are suited to the increased demand in the industry.

Sulphonamides being the first drugs acting selectively could be used systematically as preventive and therapeutic agents against various diseases^{2,3}. Various sulphonamide-imines have been synthesized and were tested for their potential pharmacological applications as antiacids⁴, antidiarrhoeal and antiulcer activities⁵. Imines continue to occupy an important position as ligands in metal coordination chemistry⁶, almost a century after their discovery. Some metal complexes of the imines derived from [N1-(4-methoxy-1,2,5-thiadiazol-3-yl)sulfanilamide] and 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde were synthesized and subjected to spectroscopic and thermal studies⁷. Organotin(IV) complexes of biologically active imines derived from condensation of 2-acetylfuran and 2-acetylthiophene with sulphaguanidine, sulphathiazole, sulphisoxazole and sulphadiazine were prepared⁶.

The organic germanium has been used clinically in many parts of the world to treat a wide spectrum of illnesses, and has been the subject of extensive research in many disciplines : pathology, biochemistry, pharmaco-

[†]In honour of Professor K. B. Pandeya on the occasion of his 70th Birth Anniversary.

logy, immunology, oncology and neurochemistry⁸. Organic germanium has been used in a broad spectrum of regimes on its own, with diet and stress counselling, and as a drug in clinical trials of cancer therapy, in conjunction with chemotherapy, radiation therapy and surgery. Drawing these sources of information together gives quite a solid overview of the fundamental aspects of organic germanium. Measurement of urinary Ge can detect occupational exposure to inorganic Ge and its compounds. It is prudent to recommend the monitoring of renal variables in workers exposed to germanium⁹. A histological comparison of the liver, spleen, bone marrow, circulating young erythrocytes, and differential count in mature male and female albino rats receiving germanium dioxide with their litter controls not receiving this compound was made¹⁰.

In this paper we have considered the chelating behaviour of sulphonamide-imines and characterization of their germanium(IV) complexes. Ligands along with their chelates have been tested *in vitro* against a number of fungal and bacterial strains and *in vivo* on male albino rats by performing their histopathological and biochemical studies and fertility test.

Experimental

Methods and materials :

Metal salts, Ph_3GeCl and Me_3GeCl as well as other chemicals were purchased from Alfa Aesar and used as such. Solvents of analytical grade were distilled from appropriate drying agents immediately prior to use. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out at CDRI, Lucknow. Germanium was determined gravimetrically as GeO_2 . Molecular weights were determined by the Rast Camphor method. Chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl's method and sulphur was estimated by the Messenger's method. The electronic spectra were recorded on a Varian-Cary/5E spectrophotometer at SAIF, IIT, Madras, Chennai. Infrared spectra of the ligands and their complexes were recorded with the help of Nicolet Megna FTIR-550 spectrophotometer on KBr pellets. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a JEOL-AL-300 FTNMR spectrometer in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ using TMS as the internal standard.

Synthesis of the sulphonamide-imines

Two different routes were employed for the synthesis of the ligands.

Microwave assisted synthesis :

For the preparation of sulphonamide-imines, sulpha-drugs, viz. sulphathiazole and sulphaguanidine were condensed with the equimolar amount of salicylanilide in ethanol. The reaction mixture was irradiated by the conventional microwave oven by taking 2–3 mL solvent. The reactions were completed in a short period (5–7 min). The resulting precipitate was then recrystallized with alcohol and dried under vacuum. These were characterized and analysed before use. Elemental analyses were conducted using the methods mentioned above and their results were found to be in good agreement with the calculated values. The imines obtained were reported in Table 1 and shown in Fig. 1.

(L_1H_2) 2-Hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamidessulphathiazole

(a)

(L_2H_2) 2-Hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamidessulphaguanidine

(b)

Fig. 1. Structure of the ligands.

Thermal method :

For comparison purposes, the above ligands were also synthesized by the thermal method. In this method, instead of few drops of ethanol, 100 mL of ethanol, was

used to dissolve the starting materials of the ligands and the contents were refluxed for nearly 3–4 h. The residue formed was separated out, filtered off, washed with water, recrystallized from ethanol and finally dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride. A comparison between thermal method and microwave method is given in Table 1.

Biochemical aspects

The synthesized organogermanium compounds and imines were tested for the *in vitro* growth inhibitory activity against pathogenic fungi, *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Alternaria alternata* and bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella*

Table 1. Physical properties and analytical data of sulphonamide-imines of salicylanilide

Ligand	Empirical formula	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Yield (%)		Time	
			C	H	N	S		Microwave method	Thermal method	Microwave method (min)	Thermal method (h)
L ₁ H ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂	109–111	58.39 (58.65)	3.85 (4.02)	12.19 (12.43)	14.06 (14.23)	442 (450.52)	90	80	5	3
L ₂ H ₂	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₃ S	132–134	50.72 (58.66)	4.39 (4.67)	16.03 (17.10)	7.18 (7.83)	408.85 (409.46)	92	76	7	4

Synthesis of the organogermanium complexes

Microwave method :

The syntheses of the complexes were completed by taking L₁H₂ and L₂H₂ in methanol and mixing with the sodium to get their sodium salts. Then the sodium salts of the ligands were irradiated with equimolar quantity of trimethylgermaniumchloride and triphenylgermaniumchloride for 5–6 min. The completion of the reaction was checked through TLC. The resulting products were dried, repeatedly washed with dry cyclohexane and methanol and finally dried in vacuo for 3–4 h (Table 2). The purity of the newly synthesized compounds was checked through TLC by using 1 : 1 (benzene : methanol; v : v) solution. It has been observed that the compounds move as a single spot and which clearly indicated the purity of the compounds.

Thermal method :

For the synthesis of the complexes, L₁H₂ and L₂H₂ taken in methanol were mixed with the equimolar amounts of sodium to get their sodium salts. Then the sodium salts of the ligand were refluxed with equimolar quantity of Ph₃GeCl and Me₃GeCl for 13–14 h. The completion of the reaction was checked through TLC. Then excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure and resulting products were dried, repeatedly washed with dry cyclohexane and methanol and finally dried in vacuo for 3–4 h.

aerogenous, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas cepacicola*. Proper temperature, necessary nutrients, and growth media free from other microorganisms were employed for the preparation of cultures of fungi and bacteria using aseptic techniques. The “Radial Growth Method” and “Paper-Disc Plate Method” were employed to evaluate the antifungal and antibacterial activities, respectively¹¹.

Antifungal activity :

A culture of the test fungus was grown on PDA medium (glucose), starch, agar-agar and 1000 mL of H₂O at 25 ± 2 °C and the compounds after being dissolved in 50, 100 and 200 ppm concentrations in methanol were mixed in the medium. The linear growth of the fungus was obtained by measuring the diameter of the colony in petriplates after four days, and the percentage inhibition was calculated by the following relationship :

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = 100(C - T) \times C^{-1},$$

where *C* and *T* are the diameters of the fungus colony in check and test plate, respectively.

Antibacterial activity :

The nutrient agar medium (peptone, beef extract, agar-agar and NaCl) and 5 mm diameter paper discs of Whatman No. 1 were used to evaluate antibacterial activity. The compounds were dissolved in dry methanol in 500 and 1000 ppm concentrations. The filter paper discs were soaked in different solutions of the compounds, dried and then placed in the petriplates previously seeded with

Table 2. Physical properties and analytical data of the organogermanium(IV) complexes of sulphoamide-imines

S.M.	Reactants (g)	Ligand	Empirical formula	Molar ratio	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Yield (%)		Time		
					C	H	N	S	Ge	Microwave method	Thermal method	Microwave method (min)	Thermal method (h)	
1.09	(CH ₃) ₃ GeCl	L ₁ H ₂	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Ge	1 : 1	52.48 (52.93)	4.28 (4.62)	9.40 (9.87)	11.08 (11.30)	12.32 (12.79)	566.89 (567.21)	90	72	5	13
1.00	(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ GeCl	L ₁ H ₂	C ₄₀ H ₃₂ N ₄ O ₃ S ₂ Ge	1 : 1	63.25 (63.77)	4.56 (4.28)	7.24 (7.43)	8.47 (8.51)	9.23 (9.63)	750.45 (753.34)	88	75	5	13
1.80	(CH ₃) ₃ GeCl	L ₂ H ₂	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₃ SGe	1 : 1	51.70 (52.44)	5.02 (5.16)	13.06 (13.20)	5.92 (6.08)	13.46 (13.78)	525.67 (526.74)	92	70	6	14
1.12	(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ GeCl	L ₂ H ₂	C ₃₈ H ₃₃ N ₅ O ₃ SGe	1 : 1	64.78 (64.07)	4.37 (4.66)	9.36 (9.83)	4.25 (4.50)	10.70 (10.19)	710.34 (712.35)	89	74	6	14

the test organism. The plates were incubated for 24–30 h at 30 ± 1 °C and the inhibition around each disc was measured.

Antifertility activity :

The present study was carried out in male albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus* of Sprague – Dawley Strain). The animals were obtained from Hamdard University, New Delhi and were acclimatized to the laboratory condition for 10–15 days before the commencement of the experiment. The animals chosen for investigations were sexually mature and healthy having weights between 150–200 g. They were kept in plastic cages measuring 12 × 10 × 8 at room temperature 20 ± 5 °C and uniform light (14:10L:D). They were feed with standard rat pellet diet and fresh water *ad libitum*. The males were cohabited with proestrus females in the ratio of 1 : 2 and only fertile were used for the studies. A hypodermic syringe having pearl point needle was used and calculated doses of the ligand and its complexes were given orally. Six animals were tested for each dose level. Control rats were given equivalent amount of vehicle. Poising symptoms and mortality were observed daily for three days, following the treatment. Results of the toxicity were analyzed statistically for the determination of LD₅₀ value of the compounds.

Experimental design

The inbred strain of Sprague-Dawley descendant rats was used. The animals were weighed weekly to see the possible changes in the body weight during the period of experimentation. The ligand and its complexes were given orally every day in the morning. The animals were divided in to the following groups each for the ligand and its complexes.

Experiment No. 1 :

The ligand (2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide)-sulphathiazole (L₁H₂) was dissolved in olive oil and administered orally to the animals. Animals were divided into four groups with six animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received ligand (L₁H₂) 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received ligand (L₁H₂) 4 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Experiment No. 2 :

The compound $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ was dissolved in olive oil vehicle and administered orally to the animals. Animals were divided into four groups, with six animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received complex $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received complex $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ 4 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Experiment No. 3 :

$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ was dissolved in olive oil vehicle and administered orally to the animals. Animals were divided into four groups with 6 animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received complex $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received complex $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_1\text{H})$ 4 mg in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Experiment No. 4 :

The ligand (2-hydroxy-*N*-phenylbenzamide)-sulphaguanidine (L_2H_2) was dissolved in olive oil and administered orally to the animals. The animals were divided into four groups, with six animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received ligand (L_2H_2) 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received ligand (L_2H_2) 4 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Experiment No. 5 :

The compound $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ was dissolved in olive oil (vehicle) and administered orally to the animals. Animals were divided into four groups, with six animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received complex $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received complex $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ 4 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Experiment No. 6 :

The compound $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ was dissolved in olive oil (vehicle) and administered orally to the animals. Animals were divided into four groups, with six animals in each group.

Group I : Intact control or vehicle treated (0.2 mL olive oil for 60 days).

Group II : Animals received complex $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ 2 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/day for 60 days.

Group III : Animals received complex $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{Ge}(\text{L}_2\text{H})$ 4 mg/rat in 0.2 mL olive oil/days for 60 days.

Mode of feeding :

Calculated doses of the ligands and their complexes mixed in vehicle (olive oil) administered through mouth by pearl point needle. After feeding animals were allowed to take normal rat feed and water *ad libitum*. Six animals of each-group were autopsied on 61st days for hematological, histological and tissue biochemical investigations.

Experimental process :

The rats were weighed and autopsied under light ether anaesthesia and the blood from the heart was collected in preheparinized tubes. The testes and accessory glands were taken out trimmed free of fat and weighed separately on electronic balance. Tissue was fixed with Bouin's fixative, cut into pieces and processed through ethanol xylene series and embedded in paraffin wax. The section was cut out at six μm and stained with Haematoxylin Eosin. The stained sections were examined for histopathological alteration.

Body and organ weights :

Initial and final body weights and weights of testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle, ventral prostate, adrenal glands and kidney, were recorded.

Fertility test :

The male rats were kept for fertility test on day 55–60 after the ligand and its complexes feeding. The rats were cohabited with normal adult proestrous females in the ratio of 1 : 2. Successful mating was confirmed by the presence of sperms in the vaginal smear. Females were separated and resulted pregnancies were noted, when dams gave birth and the number and size of the litters were recorded. Fertility was calculated in control as well as in treated groups.

Sperm density :

The total sperms were counted using hematocytometer. Testis and cauda epididymis tissues were mashed in physiologic saline (0.9% NaCl) and sodium bicarbonate solution. The sperm density was calculated in million/mL as per the dilution¹².

Sperm motility :

Rats cauda epididymides were removed immediately after the anesthesia and the weight of cauda epididymis was gently teased in specific volume of the physiological saline (0.9% NaCl) to release the spermatozoa from the tubules. The result was determined by counting both motile and non motile sperms in at least 10 separate randomly selected fields. These were expressed as percent motility by the method of Prasad *et al.*¹³.

Biochemical analysis :

Methods adopted for the estimation of parameters in tissue, blood and hematological studies were taken after the commencement of experiment to observe any adverse change if took place from the normal level. The parameters are as :

Hematological studies :

Blood was collected from heart and important parameters viz. Total Erythrocyte Counts¹³, Total Leukocyte Count¹³, Hematocrit¹⁴, Hemoglobin¹⁵ and Blood urea¹⁶ were studied.

Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) and Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) were calculated from the value of Hematocrit, Total Erythrocytes Count and Hemoglobin.

Tissue biochemistry :

Fresh frozen tissues were analyzed for total protein and sialic acid in testis, epididymis, seminal vesicle and ventral prostate¹⁷, glycogen and total cholesterol in testis and liver^{17,18}.

Histopathological studies :

Reproductive organs i.e. testes, cauda epididymis, seminal vesicle, and vas deferens were fixed in bouin's fixative and cut into pieces. Tissues were processed through ethanol-xylene series and embedded in paraffin wax (m.p. 55–62 °C). 6 µm sections were cut and stained with Harris's hematoxylin and eosin.

Statistical analysis :

All the data obtained from the above experiments were

subjected to statistical analysis. All the values of body weights, organs weights and biochemical estimations were averaged. Standard error of mean values were calculated and student 't' test was applied for standard comparison^{19,20}.

Results and discussion

Synthetic aspects :

The reactions of triphenylgermanium chloride and trimethylgermanium chloride with sulphoamide-imines in equimolar ratio proceeded with the formation of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Ge}(\text{O}^-\text{N}^-\text{NH})$ and $\text{Me}_3\text{Ge}(\text{O}^-\text{N}^-\text{NH})$ complexes where, $\text{HO}^-\text{N}^-\text{NH}$ represents the donor system of the ligand molecule. These reactions are quite facile and proceed with the precipitation of NaCl. The coloured derivatives are soluble in common organic solvents and monomeric in nature as shown by their molecular weights. The molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solution in dry DMF show them to be non-electrolytes.

The spectroscopic results (UV, IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra) authenticate the proposed structures of the compounds.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the ligands and their germanium complexes show a broad band at around 366–364 nm that can be assigned to the $n-\pi^*$ transitions of the azomethine group, which undergoes a blue shift in the germanium complexes due to the polarization within the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ chromophore caused by the metal-ligand interaction. The electronic spectra of the ligands also exhibit another two bands at 242–276 and 271–290 nm. These are possibly due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions within the benzene ring and $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ band of the azomethine group, respectively.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of the ligands show broad and medium intensity band in the region 3410–3415 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ vibrations. This disappears in the spectra of germanium complexes showing thereby the deprotonation of this functional group. A strong band at 1615–1625 cm^{-1} in the ligands, is due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ vibrations. In case of germanium complexes this band undergoes a negative shift which again indicates coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the germanium atom. The chelation through azomethine nitrogen gets support by the appearance of new bands at around 680–700 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{Ge}-\text{N})$ vibrations (Table 3).

Table 3. IR spectral data of the ligands (L_1H_2 and L_2H_2) and their triorganogermanium complexes

Compd.	$\nu(NH)$	$\nu(C=N)$ (vs)	$\nu(OH)$ (b)	$\nu(Ge-N)$ (w)	$\nu Ge-O$
L_1H_2	3100-3300	1615	3410	-	-
$Ph_3Ge(L_1H)$	3100-3250	1600	-	700	850
$Me_3Ge(L_1H)$	3150-3350	1605	-	685	860
L_2H_2	3150-3350m	1625	3415	-	-
$Ph_3Ge(L_2H)$	3150-3300	1615	-	695	875
$Me_3Ge(L_2H)$	3140-3320	1610	-	680	865

vs = very strong, w = weak, s = sharp, b = broad.

1H NMR spectra :

The free ligands exhibit OH proton resonance signals at δ 12.10-12.20 ppm, which completely disappear in the case of germanium complexes. This indicates the deprotonation of OH group as a result of bonding through phenolic oxygen to the germanium atom. For the aromatic protons, the ligands show a complex multiplet in the region δ 8.76-6.62 ppm and it is observed in the region δ 8.10-6.50 ppm in the spectra of the organogermanium(IV) complexes (Table 4). Further, in the spectra of the complexes, a downfield shift in the position of the aromatic protons also indicates the coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the metal atom.

Table 4. 1H NMR spectra data (δ , ppm) of the ligands and their triorganogermanium(IV) complexes

Compd.	-NH-Ph	-NH	-OH	Aromatic
L_1H_2	10.60	10.28	12.10bs	8.20-6.62
$Ph_3Ge(L_1H)$	10.60	10.30	-	8.00-6.50
$Me_3Ge(L_1H)$	10.60	10.30	-	7.90-6.80
L_2H_2	10.70	10.65	12.20	8.76-7.50
$Ph_3Ge(L_2H)$	10.60	10.55	-	8.10-7.30
$Me_3Ge(L_2H)$	10.65	10.50	-	8.00-7.10

br = broad, m = multiplet, s = singlet.

X-Ray powder diffraction study :

The possible lattice dynamics of the finely powdered products, $(CH_3)_3Ge(L_1H)$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$ have been deduced on the basis of X-ray powder diffraction studies. The observed interplanar spacing values (d' in Å) have been measured from the diffractogram of the compound and the Miller indices h , k and l have been assigned to each d value and 2θ angles.

$(CH_3)_3Ge(L_1H)$:

The results show that the compound belongs to 'Monoclinic' crystal system having unit cell parameters as $a = 9.461$, $b = 9.017$, $c = 6.12$, 2θ start = 9.99, 2θ end =

89.97 and $\alpha = 90$, $\beta = 90$, $\gamma = 120$ at the wavelength = 1.54178.

$(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$:

The results show that the compound belongs to 'Monoclinic' crystal system having unit cell parameters as $a = 8.342$, $b = 8.983$, $c = 5.465$, 2θ start = 9.99, 2θ end = 89.97 and $\alpha = 90$, $\beta = 90$, $\gamma = 120$ at the wavelength = 1.54178.

Based on these studies a trigonal bipyramidal geometry has been proposed for the germanium complexes (Fig. 2).

$(CH_3)_3Ge(L_2H)$

Fig. 2. Structure of the complex.

Biological aspects

Bacterial and fungicidal activities :

Fungicidal and bactericidal activities of the imines and their corresponding organogermanium(IV) complexes

against pathogenic fungi and bacteria are recorded. The results are quite promising. The antimicrobial data reveal that the complexes are superior to the free imines. The enhanced activity of the germanium complexes may be ascribed to the increased lipophilic nature of these complexes arising due to the chelation²¹. The activity increased as the concentration was increased. Further, the results of bioactivity were compared with the conventional fungicide *Bavistin* and the conventional bactericide *Streptomycin*, taken as standards in either case.

In case of fungicidal activity, it has been observed that all of the organogermanium(IV) complexes were able to inhibit and kill the pathogens at 50-ppm concentration, while at the 100-ppm concentration of only the standard proved invariably fatal. In case of the bactericidal activity, the germanium complexes exhibited remarkable potential in inhibiting the growth of pathogens. It is emphasized that in some cases the complexes were found to be even more active than the standard *Streptomycin* against Gram-negative bacteria. Thus, it can be postulated that further intensive studies of these complexes in this direction as well as in agriculture could lead to the interesting results.

Antiandrogenic effect (antifertility activity) :

For checking the efficiency of these compounds as well as the imines, some experiments have been done on male albino rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). The rats selected for these studies were with the weights between 200–250 g. These rats were regularly checked for any disease and if found infected were isolated and treated. The rats were fed on a diet of rat feed pellets obtained from Hindustan Lever Limited, Mumbai and water was provided *ad libitum*. During, these experiments doses of the imines and their compounds were given orally after mixing in olive oil with the help of hypodermic syringe having pearl point needle for 60 days and withdrawal for 30 days. After the completion of the treatment, the fertility test was done. On day 61st, the rats were autopsied and blood was extracted from the heart. The serum was separated and used for serum biochemistry. Reproductive tissues and vital organs were blotted free of blood, weighed and used for the tissue biochemistry. The following observations were recorded :

The treatments with the ligands (L₁H₂) and (L₂H₂) and their complexes (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H), (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H), (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H), (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) were carried out at two dose levels e.g. 2 mg and 4 mg for 60 days (Tables 5–34).

Table 5. Body and organ weights of control and ligand L₁H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)				Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal
Group-I	180.69 ± 5.08	201.20 ± 4.09	1063.32 ± 2.76	380.08 ± 1.72	384.85 ± 1.53	366.84 ± 2.25	685.09 ± 11.92	32.14 ± 2.12
Control								
Group-II	183.36 ± 8.04	204.61 ± 8.05	890.41 ± 1.83**	322.30 ± 2.02**	346.38 ± 2.14**	309.39 ± 1.75**	690.51 ± 9.57 ^{ns}	30.73 ± 2.23 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	192.73 ± 6.02	204.29 ± 3.56	763.20 ± 2.06**	297.80 ± 1.14**	302.15 ± 1.64**	263.71 ± 1.68**	682.42 ± 14.02 ^{ns}	26.43 ± 1.56 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 6. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and ligand L₁H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%) (Cauda epididymis)	Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test (%)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
		Testes	Cauda epididymis			
Group-I Control	73.10 ± 0.04	4.76 ± 0.15	39.70 ± 0.42	98 (+ve)	4.24 ± 0.51	4.24 ± 0.51
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	62.00 ± 1.63*	2.69 ± 0.07**	27.83 ± 0.37**	50 (-ve)	3.89 ± 0.28	3.89 ± 0.28*
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	32.09 ± 5.92**	2.32 ± 0.06**	21.86 ± 1.56**	65 (-ve)	3.44 ± 0.36	3.44 ± 0.36**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = $P \leq 0.01$ significant, ** = $P \leq 0.001$ highly significant.

Table 7. Tissue biochemistry of control and ligand L₁H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)				Sialic acid (mg/g)		
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Prostate gland
Group-I Control	198.62 ± 4.5	210.33 ± 11.60	218.49 ± 7.40	169.06 ± 0.05	6.00 ± 0.07	5.01 ± 0.06	5.10 ± 0.15
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	192.30 ± 3.04 ^{ns}	190.45 ± 5.41*	182.00 ± 6.70*	195.32 ± 0.13*	3.94 ± 0.20**	3.85 ± 0.13**	4.05 ± 0.04**
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	183.21 ± 5.50*	160.34 ± 10.26**	158.46 ± 8.30**	148.30 ± 0.05**	3.09 ± 0.19**	3.36 ± 0.04**	3.40 ± 0.09**

ns = non significant, * = $P \leq 0.01$ significant, ** = $P \leq 0.001$ highly significant.

Table 8. Tissue biochemistry of control and ligand L₁H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I	3.96 ± 0.13	7.02 ± 0.36	11.15 ± 0.50	16.59 ± 0.18
Control				
Group-II	2.65 ± 0.19**	6.92 ± 2.15 ^{ns}	10.06 ± 0.31*	16.03 ± 5.39 ⁿ
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				
Group-III	2.60 ± 0.10**	6.83 ± 4.63 ^{ns}	8.42 ± 0.08**	15.96 ± 3.44 ⁿ
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 9. Blood analysis of control and ligand L₁H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)	Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)	Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) (Pg.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)	Blood urea (mg/dl)
Group-I	5.20 ± 0.14	8852.12 ± 14.85	15.21 ± 6.14	41.77 ± 3.42	75.02 ± 6.21	29.92 ± 2.10	31.05 ± 4.03	38.94 ± 1.80
Control								
Group-II	4.90 ± 2.13 ^{ns}	8800.00 ± 13.42 ^{ns}	14.98 ± 2.16 ^{ns}	40.06 ± 2.65 ^{ns}	80.58 ± 12.05 ^{ns}	28.65 ± 2.39 ^{ns}	31.08 ± 3.20 ^{ns}	8.20 ± 2.05 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	4.87 ± 1.25 ^{ns}	8840.02 ± 14.60 ^{ns}	14.26 ± 6.04 ^{ns}	40.98 ± 2.64 ^{ns}	80.18 ± 1.26 ^{ns}	29.34 ± 2.54 ^{ns}	31.92 ± 2.57 ^{ns}	8.36 ± 2.22 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant.

Table 10. Body and organ weights of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body. wt.)				Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body. wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal
Group-I Control	194.20 ± 8.16	200.51 ± 9.21	1052.85 ± 5.39	409.34 ± 11.20	403.20 ± 1.70	382.33 ± 0.23	721.31 ± 0.05	24.50 ± 1.20
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	190.00 ± 7.11	196.00 ± 7.54	854.51 ± 0.21**	402.00 ± 18.50**	350.20 ± 5.20**	276.80 ± 0.44**	680.25 ± 2.60 ^{ns}	24.00 ± 2.60 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	192.13 ± 4.00	200.00 ± 6.26	745.00 ± 6.24**	207.80 ± 3.45**	201.23 ± 0.05**	212.62 ± 1.54**	698.87 ± 4.50 ^{ns}	25.12 ± 7.50 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 Significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 11. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%) (Cauda epididymis)	Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
		Testes	Cauda epididymis		
Group-I Control	72.23 ± 0.43	5.23 ± 0.08	42.62 ± 2.10	98 (+ve)	4.24 ± 0.51
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	40.42 ± 2.32**	2.68 ± 0.25*	25.63 ± 0.26*	60 (-ve)	3.60 ± 0.20*
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	28.78 ± 2.16**	2.24 ± 0.56*	18.32 ± 1.54**	78 (-ve)	3.24 ± 0.36**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 12. Tissue biochemistry of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)					Sialic acid (mg/g)						
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland
Group-I Control	268.02 ± 1.36	224.42 ± 0.13	225.05 ± 1.45	192.10 ± 0.08	5.98 ± 0.68	4.94 ± 0.21	5.57 ± 0.06	5.67 ± 0.82				
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	257.72 ± 5.62*	183.20 ± 4.20*	188.06 ± 2.26*	186.25 ± 0.10*	3.76 ± 0.63*	4.40 ± 0.09*	3.86 ± 0.02**	4.90 ± 1.56*				
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	180.10 ± 4.75**	156.03 ± 0.05**	145.02 ± 7.63**	149.32 ± 0.45**	3.00 ± 0.49**	2.52 ± 0.01**	3.20 ± 0.28**	3.32 ± 0.17**				

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 13. Tissue biochemistry of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I Control	3.93 ± 0.02	4.83 ± 0.32	10.98 ± 0.51	16.46 ± 0.12
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	2.50 ± 0.16**	4.66 ± 0.04 ^{ns}	10.06 ± 0.06 ^{ns}	16.82 ± 0.07 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	2.09 ± 0.05**	4.40 ± 2.00 ^{ns}	6.42 ± 0.89 ^{ns}	16.43 ± 0.05 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 Significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 14. Blood analysis of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)	Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)	Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH) (Pg.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)	Blood urea (mg/dl)
Group-I Control	5.10 ± 0.02	8016.00 ± 23.03	16.02 ± 0.02	45.23 ± 0.06	80.16 ± 0.05	28.12 ± 0.50	29.18 ± 0.03	38.24 ± 0.06
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	4.88 ± 0.32 ^{ns}	8070.00 ± 14.86 ^{ns}	15.94 ± 0.62 ^{ns}	49.50 ± 0.42 ^{ns}	79.63 ± 0.22 ^{ns}	26.20 ± 0.20 ^{ns}	30.62 ± 0.50 ^{ns}	40.20 ± 0.40 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	5.00 ± 0.06 ^{ns}	8010.00 ± 23.93 ^{ns}	16.21 ± 0.07 ^{ns}	45.51 ± 0.05 ^{ns}	78.31 ± 0.08 ^{ns}	28.14 ± 0.30 ^{ns}	30.94 ± 0.05 ^{ns}	39.24 ± 0.08 ^{ns}

ns = Non significant.

Table 15. Body and organ weights of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)					Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal	
Group-I Control	209.00 ± 3.60	205.02 ± 2.98	1094.83 ± 1.07	349.54 ± 0.14	414.83 ± 7.15	396.26 ± 8.05	821.01 ± 10.92	38.18 ± 0.30	
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	189.00 ± 2.60*	190.00 ± 4.54**	998.56 ± 2.04*	246.20 ± 6.22**	310.50 ± 3.31**	283.21 ± 4.63**	810.87 ± 0.02 ^{ns}	37.67 ± 0.05 ^{ns}	
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	196.13 ± 2.00*	200.00 ± 4.26**	930.21 ± 1.62**	238.09 ± 2.05**	268.24 ± 11.26**	208.32 ± 8.62**	808.45 ± 16.04 ^{ns}	38.14 ± 2.34 ^{ns}	

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 16. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%)		Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test (%)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
	(Cauda epididymis)	Testes	Cauda epididymis	Testes		
Group-I	68.72 ± 2.50	4.75 ± 0.42	42.45 ± 2.73	98 (+ve)	4.24 ± 0.51	
Control						
Group-II	50.52 ± 3.62*	2.08 ± 0.09**	28.70 ± 2.90**	70 (-ve)	3.00 ± 0.20*	
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days						
Group-III	20.45 ± 1.93**	1.18 ± 0.01**	12.74 ± 3.32**	85 (-ve)	2.74 ± 0.26**	
4mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days						

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01, significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 17. Tissue biochemistry of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)					Sialic acid (mg/g)		
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland
Group-I	240.63 ± 6.23	207.64 ± 8.23	223.02 ± 4.62	202.04 ± 3.94	5.10 ± 0.25	4.72 ± 0.30	5.43 ± 0.03	5.37 ± 0.39
Control								
Group-II	173.01 ± 9.20*	178.36 ± 4.60*	190.26 ± 10.63*	152.49 ± 5.62*	3.68 ± 0.05*	3.81 ± 0.76*	4.89 ± 0.05*	4.26 ± 0.83*
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	153.26 ± 15.24**	140.02 ± 8.35**	180.23 ± 4.06**	140.19 ± 0.83**	3.52 ± 0.30**	3.05 ± 0.02**	4.03 ± 0.06**	4.02 ± 0.68**
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 18. Tissue biochemistry of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H) treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I	3.69 ± 0.03	6.98 ± 0.05	10.26 ± 1.45	14.79 ± 0.88
Control				
Group-II	2.58 ± 0.05**	6.73 ± 0.45 ^{ns}	10.08 ± 0.28 ^{ns}	14.03 ± 2.63 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				
Group-III	2.06 ± 0.06**	6.96 ± 0.30 ^{ns}	8.09 ± 0.05*	13.98 ± 1.44 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 19. Blood analysis of control and $(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$ treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)	Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)	Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCH) (Pg.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)	Blood urea (mg/dl)
Group-I	5.02 ± 0.05	8182.82 ± 30.65	14.17 ± 0.03	48.56 ± 2.98	82.62 ± 5.40	39.52 ± 0.50	30.76 ± 0.30	38.65 ± 2.75
Control								
Group-II	4.92 ± 0.03 ^{ns}	8280.25 ± 35.10 ^{ns}	13.58 ± 0.20.16 ^{ns}	47.92 ± 4.76 ^{ns}	83.04 ± 0.05 ^{ns}	39.95 ± 0.06 ^{ns}	31.09 ± 0.06 ^{ns}	36.80 ± 3.05 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	4.89 ± 0.16 ^{ns}	8117.02 ± 32.59 ^{ns}	13.98 ± 0.95 ^{ns}	48.21 ± 0.03 ^{ns}	82.23 ± 0.03 ^{ns}	39.02 ± 0.04 ^{ns}	30.95 ± 0.08 ^{ns}	36.89 ± 3.89 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant.

Table 20. Body and organ weights of control and ligand L_2H_2 treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)				Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal
Group-I	180.32 ± 10.02	184.20 ± 8.09	1052.01 ± 4.34	308.35 ± 1.22	384.85 ± 1.53	366.84 ± 2.25	685.09 ± 11.92	32.14 ± 2.12
Control								
Group-II	195.16 ± 8.04	190.01 ± 6.02	856.21 ± 5.36 ^{**}	265.10 ± 4.04 ^{**}	346.38 ± 2.14 ^{**}	309.39 ± 1.75 ^{**}	690.51 ± 9.57 ^{ns}	30.73 ± 2.23 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	189.71 ± 6.02	186.16 ± 6.52	751.20 ± 5.00 ^{**}	179.20 ± 4.04 ^{**}	302.15 ± 1.64 ^{**}	263.71 ± 1.68 ^{**}	682.42 ± 14.02 ^{ns}	26.43 ± 1.56 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant * = $P \leq 0.01$ significant, ** = $P \leq 0.001$ highly significant.

Table 21. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and ligand L₂H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%)		Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test (%)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
	(Cauda epididymis)	Testes	Cauda epididymis	Testes		
Group-I	73.10 ± 0.04	4.76 ± 0.15	39.70 ± 0.42	98 (+ve)	4024 ± 0.51	
Control						
Group-II	62.00 ± 1.63**	2.69 ± 0.07**	17.83 ± 1.37**	70 (-ve)	3.29 ± 0.28	
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days						
Group-III	22.09 ± 5.92**	1.82 ± 0.06**	11.86 ± 1.56**	90 (-ve)	2.14 ± 0.36	
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days						

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 22. Tissue biochemistry of control and ligand L₂H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)				Sialic acid (mg/g)			
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland
Group-I	226.02 ± 2.9	200.06 ± 12.03	214.36 ± 9.20	211.03 ± 0.08	5.11 ± 0.05	4.92 ± 0.03	5.00 ± 0.09	4.15 ± 0.25
Control								
Group-II	183.14 ± 3.69 ^{ns}	180.00 ± 6.39*	176.49 ± 8.94*	179.32 ± 0.23**	3.74 ± 0.02**	3.50 ± 0.23**	4.10 ± 0.06**	3.91 ± 0.06**
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								
Group-III	171.04 ± 0.03*	154.78 ± 15.06**	152.43 ± 9.63**	143.00 ± 0.09**	3.14 ± 0.23**	3.03 ± 0.06**	3.51 ± 0.04**	3.10 ± 0.06**
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days								

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 23. Tissue biochemistry of control and ligand L₂H₂ treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I	3.72 ± 0.42	6.98 ± 0.41	10.94 ± 0.68	16.17 ± 0.25
Control				
Group-II	2.19 ± 0.10**	6.65 ± 0.25 ^{ns}	10.00 ± 0.42*	15.94 ± 1.12 ^{ns}
2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				
Group-III	2.10 ± 0.20**	6.84 ± 0.12 ^{ns}	9.12 ± 0.06**	15.81 ± 3.16 ^{ns}
4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days				

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 24. Blood analysis of control and ligand L₂H₃ treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)	Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)	Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCH) (Pg.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)	Blood urea (mg/dl)
Group-I Control	5.00 ± 0.68	8512.68 ± 11.26	14.26 ± 7.84	39.72 ± 2.16	74.10 ± 3.41	29.20 ± 4.62	30.76 ± 2.03	38.45 ± 2.60
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	4.89 ± 4.03 ^{ns}	8500.12 ± 14.74 ^{ns}	14.00 ± 3.12 ^{ns}	38.15 ± 3.14 ^{ns}	79.80 ± 11.54 ^{ns}	28.66 ± 3.12 ^{ns}	30.16 ± 4.12 ^{ns}	38.06 ± 2.21 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	4.72 ± 1.92 ^{ns}	8490.62 ± 13.62 ^{ns}	13.73 ± 8.19 ^{ns}	37.65 ± 2.84 ^{ns}	79.13 ± 10.16 ^{ns}	27.01 ± 5.14 ^{ns}	30.82 ± 4.69 ^{ns}	38.29 ± 3.62 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant.

Table 25. Body and organ weights of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)				Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal
Group-I Control	177.33 ± 6.49	174.43 ± 8.86	1025.24 ± 4.15	311.87 ± 1.11	494.49 ± 2.92	356.60 ± 0.31	802.02 ± 13.00	31.00 ± 0.36
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	170.19 ± 7.81	175.72 ± 9.32	920.92 ± 3.53 ^{**}	240.78 ± 3.94 ^{**}	325.93 ± 2.81 ^{**}	253.67 ± 2.21 ^{**}	806.00 ± 3.26 ^{ns}	30.05 ± 2.26 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	184.34 ± 5.26	193.26 ± 2.58	908.75 ± 21.06 ^{**}	196.54 ± 9.42 ^{**}	280.74 ± 2.63 ^{**}	198.43 ± 1.43 ^{**}	784.23 ± 4.20 ^{ns}	30.98 ± 1.48 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 26. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%)		Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test (%)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
	(Cauda epididymis)	Testes	Cauda epididymis	Testes		
Group-I Control	71.26 ± 2.5	5.23 ± 0.13	38.62 ± 2.5		98 (+ve)	4.24 ± 0.51
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	45.45 ± 0.06**	4.75 ± 0.20*	32.05 ± 1.6*		40 (-ve)	3.42 ± 0.458
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	20.29 ± 1.55**	2.05 ± 0.42**	18.95 ± 3.15*		75 (-ve)	2.66 ± 0.28**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 27. Tissue biochemistry of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)				Sialic acid (mg/g)			
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland
Group-I Control	246.20 ± 1.92	228.92 ± 6.29	240.01 ± 1.35	220.00 ± 1.54	6.94 ± 2.92	5.34 ± 0.68	5.15 ± 0.42	4.76 ± 0.20
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	180.43 ± 12.62*	188.04 ± 13.04*	220.01 ± 7.89*	205.14 ± 2.79*	5.82 ± 0.13*	4.59 ± 0.13*	3.85 ± 0.69*	3.09 ± 0.42*
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	158.12 ± 10.62**	146.00 ± 7.35**	186.11 ± 2.43**	179.53 ± 1.26**	4.08 ± 0.10**	3.76 ± 0.68**	3.04 ± 0.56**	2.61 ± 0.15**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 Significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 28. Tissue biochemistry of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I Control	3.21 ± 0.04	6.93 ± 0.28	12.24 ± 0.36	14.82 ± 0.63
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	2.84 ± 0.69*	6.90 ± 0.12 ^{ns}	10.06 ± 0.19**	14.32 ± 0.03 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	2.04 ± 0.05**	6.38 ± 0.83 ^{ns}	9.56 ± 0.08**	14.46 ± 0.82 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 29. Blood analysis of control and (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)	Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)	Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCH) (Pg.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)	Blood urea (mg/dl)
Group-I Control	5.92 ± 0.13	8853.32 ± 40.64	15.09 ± 0.12	46.32 ± 2.60	80.26 ± 0.32	27.05 ± 0.52	31.05 ± 0.36	50.62 ± 0.05
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	6.08 ± 1.06 ^{ns}	8654.06 ± 52.12 ^{ns}	14.96 ± 2.09 ^{ns}	45.68 ± 3.03 ^{ns}	79.62 ± 3.04 ^{ns}	25.93 ± 2.09 ^{ns}	26.05 ± 2.26 ^{ns}	49.00 ± 3.03 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	5.96 ± 1.02 ^{ns}	8761.49 ± 5.86 ^{ns}	14.87 ± 2.40 ^{ns}	45.81 ± 1.62 ^{ns}	78.10 ± 1.06 ^{ns}	25.12 ± 1.03 ^{ns}	25.82 ± 1.08 ^{ns}	48.63 ± 2.04 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant.

Table 30. Body and organ weights of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Body weight (g)		Reproductive organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)				Vital organs weight (mg/100 g body wt.)	
	Initial	Final	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Kidney	Adrenal
Group-I Control	209.34 ± 7.13	198.20 ± 7.06	1345.33 ± 10.21	330.21 ± 6.00	235.71 ± 8.22	297.62 ± 4.00	724.62 ± 6.14	37.45 ± 0.68
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	195.42 ± 9.18	200.17 ± 6.06	1083.27 ± 10.15**	241.41 ± 2.18**	202.95 ± 5.80**	226.43 ± 5.21**	712.00 ± 1.18 ^{ns}	36.78 ± 1.20 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	199.00 ± 5.23	198.63 ± 6.62	1002.14 ± 13.56**	200.00 ± 8.09**	176.45 ± 8.06**	210.54 ± 6.26**	729.64 ± 1.06 ^{ns}	36.49 ± 1.16 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 31. Sperm dynamics and fertility of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Sperm motility (%)		Sperm density (million/mL)		Fertility test (%)	Serum testosterone (µg/mL)
	(Cauda epididymis)	(Cauda epididymis)	Testes	Cauda epididymis		
Group-I Control	70.23 ± 1.22	47.68 ± 1.38**	4.99 ± 0.02	39.68 ± 4.62	98 (+ve)	4.24 ± 0.51
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	19.68 ± 2.65**	47.68 ± 1.38**	2.95 ± 0.26**	26.43 ± 1.07**	65 (-ve)	3.09 ± 0.28*
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	19.68 ± 2.65**	19.68 ± 2.65**	1.47 ± 0.62**	12.97 ± 2.31**	80 (-ve)	2.04 ± 0.36**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 32. Tissue biochemistry of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Protein (mg/g)				Sialic acid (mg/g)			
	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland	Testes	Epididymis	Seminal vesicle	Prostate gland
Group-I Control	200.08 ± 0.03	215.00 ± 9.20	173.45 ± 0.65	203.40 ± 7.00	5.93 ± 0.06	6.20 ± 0.20	6.30 ± 0.18	4.56 ± 0.65
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	198.43 ± 0.90*	180.43 ± 10.10*	164.10 ± 0.60*	145.32 ± 18.00*	5.09 ± 0.30**	5.04 ± 0.63**	5.13 ± 0.10**	4.20 ± 0.50**
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	149.63 ± 5.40**	115.31 ± 10.90**	126.29 ± 0.26**	110.80 ± 17.00**	3.80 ± 0.80**	3.76 ± 0.68**	3.04 ± 0.56**	2.61 ± 0.15**

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 33. Tissue biochemistry of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Glycogen (mg/g)		Cholesterol (mg/g)	
	Testes	Liver	Testes	Liver
Group-I Control	2.88 ± 0.56	4.95 ± 0.26	9.86 ± 1.03	15.95 ± 0.29
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	1.68 ± 0.031*	4.93 ± 0.92 ^{ns}	8.23 ± 0.80*	14.92 ± 0.02 ^{ns}
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days	1.59 ± 1.48**	4.89 ± 1.08 ^{ns}	5.69 ± 0.23**	14.83 ± 0.05 ^{ns}

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant, * = P ≤ 0.01 significant, ** = P ≤ 0.001 highly significant.

Table 34. Blood analysis of control and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated rats

Treatment	Total Erythrocyte Count (TEC) (million/mm ³)		Total Leukocyte Count (TLC) (per cu. mm)		Hemoglobin (Hb) (g%)	Hematocrit (PCV) (%)	Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) (cu.)	Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCH) (Pg.)		Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC) (%)		Blood urea (mg/dl)
	5.30 ± 0.04	5.02 ± 2.02 ^{ns}	8013.25 ± 4.86	7920.45 ± 3.20 ^{ns}				26.32 ± 0.04	23.01 ± 3.92 ^{ns}	31.14 ± 0.09	36.25 ± 0.02	
Control												
Group-II 2 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days					13.86 ± 0.20	42.12 ± 0.04	78.62 ± 0.06	26.32 ± 0.04	31.14 ± 0.09	36.25 ± 0.02		
Group-III 4 mg/kg body wt./day for 60 days					13.84 ± 1.06 ^{ns}	41.66 ± 3.30 ^{ns}	72.01 ± 2.30 ^{ns}	23.01 ± 3.92 ^{ns}	32.42 ± 4.42 ^{ns}	35.96 ± 3.20 ^{ns}		
					13.62 ± 2.01 ^{ns}	42.42 ± 1.05 ^{ns}	80.02 ± 2.01 ^{ns}	26.14 ± 2.07 ^{ns}	33.19 ± 1.04 ^{ns}	34.00 ± 1.01 ^{ns}		

(Mean ± SEM of 10 animals), ns = non significant.

WEIGHT RESPONSE

Body weight :

The body weight of control group receiving ligands (L₁H₂) and (L₂H₂) and their complexes (CH₃)₃Ge(L₁H), (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₁H), (CH₃)₃Ge(L₂H) and (C₆H₅)₃Ge(L₂H) treated animals showed no significant change in their body weights when compared with their initial body weights.

Organ weight :

Testes :

A higher significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in the weights of testes was observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels after oral administration of the ligands and their complexes in comparison to the control animal.

Epididymis :

Oral administration of both the doses of the ligands and their complexes to rats caused a highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in the weights of epididymis in comparison to the control animals.

Seminal vesicle :

A highly significant decrease ($P \leq 0.001$) in seminal vesicles weight was observed after oral administration of the ligands and their complexes at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels for 60 days.

Prostate gland :

A highly significant loss ($P \leq 0.001$) in the prostate gland weights was observed when ligands and their complexes were administrated at 2 mg and 4 mg levels.

Kidney :

Statistically, non-significant change was observed in the weights of kidney in the rats treated with different doses of ligands and complexes as compared to the control rats.

Adrenal gland :

Non-significant change in the weights of adrenal glands in the rats treated with the different doses of the ligands and their complexes was observed.

SPERM DYNAMICS

Sperm motility :

Cauda epididymis :

A significant reduction ($P \leq 0.01$) was observed at 2 mg dose level whereas a highly significant reduction ($P \leq$

0.001) was observed at 4 mg dose level in case of (L_1H_2) and ($(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$) and a highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) was observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels in case of remaining complexes.

Sperm density :

Testes :

Highly significant reductions in testicular sperm density were observed when rats were fed with the (L_1H_2), ($(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$), L_2H_2 and ($(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_2H)$) and significant reductions were observed when rats were fed with the ($(CH_3)_3Ge(L_1H)$) and ($(CH_3)_3Ge(L_2H)$).

Cauda epididymis :

The density of sperm in cauda epididymis was reduced highly significantly ($P \leq 0.001$) after the treatment with the ligands and their complexes.

Fertility test :

Negative fertility were recorded when the male rats were fed with the ligands and their complexes at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels.

Radio-immuno assays (RIA) :

Testosterone – A significant decline was observed when the male rats were fed with ligands and their complexes at 2 mg dose level while highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) reduction was observed at 4 mg dose level.

TISSUE BIOCHEMISTRY

Protein :

Testes :

In the testes of rats protein content was decreased significantly ($P \leq 0.01$) when the male rats were fed with ligands (L_1H_2) and (L_2H_2) at 4 mg dose level where as 2 mg dose level had no effect on testes, protein concentration and oral administration of complexes to rats caused significant to highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$ to $P \leq 0.001$) reduction in the protein contents of testes at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels as compared with the control.

Epididymis :

Oral administration of the ligands and their complexes caused significant reduction in the epididymis protein contents at 2 mg dose level whereas highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in group-III was observed as compared to the control.

Seminal vesicle :

A significant to highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$ to $P \leq 0.001$) reduction in seminal vesicle protein contents was observed after 2 mg and 4 mg ligands and complexes treatment when compared with control rats.

Prostate gland :

A significant to highly significant ($P \leq 0.01$ to $P \leq 0.001$) decrease was observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels in the protein contents of prostate gland of the L_1H_2 , ($(CH_3)_3Ge(L_1H)$), ($(CH_3)_3Ge(L_2H)$) and ($(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_2H)$) treated rats in comparison to the control and highly significant decrease was observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels in the protein contents of prostate gland of the L_2H_2 and ($(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$).

Sialic acid :

Testes :

Oral administration of the ligands to the rats caused highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in the sialic acid concentration at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels and significant to highly significant alteration in the sialic acid contents of testes of complexes treated rats were observed ($P \leq 0.01$) at 2 mg and ($P \leq 0.001$) at 4 mg when statistically compared with the control Group-I.

Epididymis :

A highly significant reduction in the ligands L_1H_2 and L_2H_2 treated epididymis sialic acid concentration at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels was observed as compared to the vehicle treated control Group-I and a significant ($P \leq 0.01$) reduction was observed in the sialic acid contents of epididymis of complexes at 2 mg dose level, where as a highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) decrease at 4 mg dose level in comparison to the control rats.

Seminal vesicle :

A highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in the sialic acid contents of seminal vesicle was observed after 2 mg and 4 mg treatment to rats when compared with the control.

Prostate gland :

A highly significant change ($P \leq 0.001$) and significant to highly significant were observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels with comparison to the control.

Glycogen :

Testes :

A highly significant reduction ($P \leq 0.001$) in glycogen contents of testes of ligands and their complexes treated rats was observed at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels respectively as compared with the control.

Liver :

Non-significant changes were observed in the ligands and their complexes treated rats, in liver glycogen contents at two dose levels as compared to the control.

Cholesterol :

Testes :

Non-significant changes in the cholesterol contents of testes at 4 mg and 2 mg dose levels of L_1H_2 and $(CH_3)_3Ge(L_1H)$, while non-significant change ($P \leq 0.01$) at 2 mg dose level and significant change ($P \leq 0.001$) at 4 mg dose levels of $(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_1H)$ and significant to highly significant changes at 4 mg and 2 mg dose levels of L_2H_2 and $(C_6H_5)_3Ge(L_2H)$ and highly significant changes were observed at 4 mg and 2 mg dose levels of $(CH_3)_3Ge(L_2H)$ as compared to control Group-I.

Liver :

A non-significant alteration was observed in the ligands and their complexes treated liver cholesterol contents at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels as compared to the vehicle treated control Group-I.

Hematology :

Total erythrocyte count (TEC) :

Non significant changes were observed in the TEC counts at both the dose levels of the ligands and their complexes in comparison to the control.

Total leukocyte count (TLC) :

No changes were observed in TLC counts after oral administration of the ligands and their complexes at 2 mg and 4 mg dose levels with comparison to the control rats.

Hemoglobin :

Non significant differences were observed in the hemoglobin percentage of the rats treated with the ligands and their complexes at all dose levels.

Hematocrit :

No significant changes were observed in PCV con-

centration of 2 mg and 4 mg with the ligands and their complexes treated rats in comparison to the control.

Blood urea :

No significant differences were observed in the blood urea of 2 mg and 4 mg treated rats as compared to the control.

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL OBSERVATION

(For the ligands and their complexes)

Testes :

Control :

The testes of Group-I i.e. control rats had all the normal features and seminiferous tubules were lined with germinal epithelium. All the stages of spermatogenesis i.e. spermatogonia, primary and secondary spermatocytes and spermatids were present. The lumens of seminiferous tubules were full of spermatozoa. Nutritive cells i.e. sertoli cells were normal and present in the outermost layer of seminiferous tubules. Interstitial cells and Leydig cells were large and polyhedral with an ecutric nucleus.

2 mg/day for 60 days :

The circular section of testes treated with 2 mg ligands showed less developed spermatogenic elements. The lumen of seminiferous tubules was empty with less number of spermatozoa. When the rats treated with the complexes results indicate that lumen of seminiferous tubules filled with debris and mature spermatozoa were absent, but in the each cases interstitial cells were normal and present between seminiferous tubules. Sertoli cells were also normal in appearance.

4 mg/day for 60 days :

4 mg ligands administration caused arrest of spermatogenesis at spermatid stage. Lumen of seminiferous tubules was filled with debris of broken tail and dead spermatozoa. In the case of complexes, spermatogenesis was completely arrested. However, the damage was not uniform. In some tubules, damage was seen in the elongated spermatids lumen of the tubules contained large amount of broken sperm tails, residual sperms and detritus. Leydig cells and sertoli cells were normal in both cases.

Epididymis :

Control :

Epididymis contained large and uniform tubular di-

mensions lined by the pseudostratified epithelium with low columnar cells. The intertubular stroma contained connective tissues and blood vessels. The lumen was large and full of sperm.

2 mg/day for 60 days :

Administration of ligands and their complexes to rats at 2 mg dose levels showed some atrophical changes in the histoarchitecture of cauda epididymis as the lumen was filled with some spermatozoa and filled with debris. Epithelial cell height was also reduced.

4 mg/day for 60 days :

In 4 mg ligands treated rats, the reduction in the epithelial cell height was very conspicuous. Spermatozoa detritus was present in the lumen of tubules. Stereocilia was short and scanty but in the case of complexes, stereocilia was absent in the lumen.

Vas deferens :

Control :

The vas deferens of control rats had a narrow irregular lumen, a thin mucosa and a thick muscularis surrounded by adventitia. The epithelium was pseudostratified columnar cells resting on a thin basement membrane. Stereocilia were present. The muscularis consists of a thin inner longitudinal layer, a thick middle circular layer and a thinner but well developed outer longitudinal layer. Lumen contains numerous spermatozoa.

2 mg/day for 60 days :

The transverse section of vas deferens of 2 mg, ligands showed normal picture except lumen was devoid of spermatozoa. The epithelium was pseudostratified with stereocilia, but treatment with the complexes, vas deferens showed absence of sperms in the lumen. The luminal epithelium was normal with presence of stereocilia. The entire three muscle coats were also normal in the structure.

4 mg/day for 60 days :

Ligands and their complexes treated vas deferens showed narrow lumen without spermatozoa. Stereocilia were degenerated. Lumen was devoid of sperm.

CONCLUSION OF THE NEW FINDINGS

The weights of testes and sex accessories have always been considered as an important parameter of hormonal

assay²². It has also been observed that the oral administration of these compounds caused a significant reduction in the weight of testis and accessory sex organs at various dose levels. The reduction in the weight of testes reflects regressive changes in seminiferous tubules, which are associated with azoospermia and germinal aplasia. The changes in testicular weight have also corresponded to the presence and absence of post-meiotic germ cells. Reduction in the number of germinal cells understandably leads to reduction in the weight of testes²³. Similar reduction in testes weight was also observed in animals²⁴. Reduction in weight of accessory sex organs after treatment with ligand and its complexes directly support the reduced availability of androgen²⁵. It has been reported that accessory sex organs are dependent on circulating androgen level for maintenance of their structure and functions. The treatment exerted strong inhibitory effects on epididymis seminal vesicle and prostate gland as evidenced by decrease in their weights. The work of Malarvizhi and Mathur²⁶ suggested that compound interferes with the testosterone output, which results in decrease in seminal vesicle and prostate gland weight. It has also been suggested that rat prostate glands have receptor, specialized to respond for androgen²⁷. So reduced androgen might be the cause of decrease in weight of prostate gland in the animals treated with ligand and their compounds, because prostate development and functions were mainly depend on testicular androgens²⁸.

Sperm motility :

Sperm motility is of prime importance for the functional capacity of the sperms and assessment of the sperm motion, sperm motility can be useful in the evaluation of toxic effect on male reproductive system²⁹. Sperm quality is usually evaluated by estimating motility and density of sperms obtained from epididymis. Oral administration of the compounds and ligand lead to reduce motility of sperms in epididymis. The results of present investigations exhibited significant decline in the sperm motility of caudal sperms in rats, after treatment with ligand and its complexes suggesting impairment of the androgen supply in the epididymis, which adversely affects maturation of the spermatozoa. The other possible speculation for decline in the number of motile spermatozoa is that these compounds might be acting directly on epididymis spermatozoa and may produce morphological or func-

tional alteration of spermatozoa. Sperm motility is dependent solely on the energy in the form of ATP generated during glycolysis and oxidizing phosphorylation. The mid piece of sperm is composed of mitochondria which produce energy. It has been reported that lipid peroxidation adversely affects the sperm motility²⁴. The poor sperm motility is related with deficient antioxidant and potential of spermatozoa which protects them from adverse effect of lipid peroxidation and other manifestation of oxygen toxicity. It is observed that ligand and its germanium complexes caused an increase in the production of reactive oxygen supply by sperm in hormonal suppressed oligospermia, results in loss of motility. Reduction in motility and fertilization capacity of sperms following the administration of the ligand and its germanium complexes may be due to reduced testosterone and decreased epididymal proteins. The epididymal spermatozoa is highly dependent on testosterone and epididymal proteins for their final maturation and development of progressive motility and fertilizing capacity³⁰.

Sperm density :

It has proven that sperm density has direct correlation with fertility of sperms. In this study the ligands and their germanium complexes have been shown to reduce the density of sperms in cauda epididymis as well as testes. Reduction in sperm count in testes may be due to the altered gonadotrophins, the suppression of gonadotropin may decrease sperm density in testes. Reduction in sperm density in cauda epididymis is due to alteration in androgen metabolism. It is well known that physiological and biochemical integration of epididymis are dependent on androgen. Androgens are the hormones, which cause the formation of spermatozoa and their motility and capacity to fertilize ova. Reduced motility of sperms shows less secretion of androgens from Leydig cells and thus reflects antiandrogenic nature of the compounds. Reduced sperm density in testes is due to decrease in androgen level³¹.

Hematological studies :

Blood is sensitive indicator of toxicant induced stress. The studies of bloods are useful in the detection and diagnosis of metabolic disturbance and disease processes. The blood consists of plasma and cellular components, which form part of a unique system in the body.

Total erythrocyte count :

No change was observed in the total erythrocyte count following the administration of the ligands and their germanium complexes. A little decrease was observed in total erythrocyte count after 4 mg germanium compounds administration. Decrease in total erythrocyte count reflects deficiency of vitamin B₁₂ or folic acid because two factors are essential for the proper maturation and production of total red cells in bone marrow. These two factors are vitamin B₁₂ and folic acid. Vitamin B₁₂ is stored in the liver and its deficiency is characterized by disturbance in erythropoiesis. Deficiency of vitamin B₁₂ leads to impaired synthesis of nucleic acid resulting in defective maturation of erythrocytes and their nuclei³².

Total leukocyte counts (TLC) :

The total leukocyte counts of germanium compounds after the treatment were in normal limits. This shows that there was no ill effect on the immune system of the rats.

Hemoglobin :

The most important function of hemoglobin is to carry oxygen from the inspired air in the lungs and deliver it to the tissues. Hemoglobin concentration was in normal limits following the administration of the ligand and its organogermanium complexes, whereas a decrease was found in high doses (4 mg/day) of germanium complexes. The decrease in hemoglobin may be due to increase in the rate at which the hemoglobin is destroyed. The rate of the hemoglobin destruction increase due to destruction of erythrocytes at high doses of germanium complexes³³. In this studies a decrease in hemoglobin may be due to decrease in oxidation rate of hemoglobin after high dose of germanium complexes.

Hematocrit :

The hematocrit percentage was normal after ligand and its organogermanium complexes treatment, whereas decrease in the hematocrit percentage after 4 mg organogermanium complexes treatment was due to either a decrease in the size of RBC or a decrease in the number of erythrocyte. The decrease in the size of RBC or decrease in number of RBC shows toxic effect of germanium complexes on general metabolism.

Blood urea :

No change was observed in the blood urea following

the oral administration of ligand and its organogermanium complexes at lower dose level. An increase in the blood urea of high doses (4 mg) organogermanium complexes was observed. It may be due to a high concentration of urea in the body fluids. High dose of germanium compounds has toxic effect on kidney, so that kidney was not able to filter urea from the blood, hence increased in the blood urea was observed.

Biochemistry :

Glycogen :

Glycogen is an important energy source in animals and human. It is also considered essential for gonadal maturation and their proper functioning. The presence of glycogen has been reported in Sertoli cells and germinal cells of the testes of various mammalian species. Constant supply of carbohydrate (Glucose) is essential for gonadal maturation and the proper functioning of the testes. Reduction in testicular glycogen contents were noticed after treatment with the ligand and its germanium complexes. The reduced level of glycogen may be due to interference in glucose metabolism. Leydig cell function is also suppressed in the absence of carbohydrate. The treatment of rats with ligand and its complexes may affect activity of glycolytic enzymes directly or indirectly which may affect the maturational process of spermatozoa and their motility. Decrease in testicular glycogen possibly attributed in decreased number of post-meiotic germ cells, spermatocyte and spermatid which are more sensitive as compared to other germinal cells in glucose stimulated protein synthesis.

The reduced level of glycogen in liver might be due to some metabolic changes induced by the ligand and its complex. The reduction in glycogen in this study agrees with the earlier findings³⁴. Approximately two third of the free glucose entering the liver is phosphorylate to glucose-6-phosphate and its subsequently converted in to glycogen fatty acid or blood glucose. The glycogen conversion process may have been affected as the hepatocytes (sites of glycogen conversion) were necrotic as observed in this study and the liver glycogen was decreased.

Cholesterol :

The role of cholesterol differs in the two compartments of the testes. In the interstitial tissue, cholesterol is necessary for the synthesis of testosterone, whereas in

the seminiferous tubule membrane cholesterol content in developing germ cells will influence the gamete fertility³⁵. Cholesterol level plays an important role in the synthesis of steroid hormones and its level in relation to fertility of individual. Cholesterol besides being a common physical precursor of all steroid hormones also plays an important role in maintenance of cell membranes. The oral administration of the ligand and its organogermanium complexes decreased the testicular cholesterol. Cholesterol acts as basic substances for the synthesis of testosterone hormones and Leydig cells of testes continuously utilize cholesterol from circulating hormone for synthesis of androgen³⁶. Decreased testicular cholesterol after ligand and its complex treatment reflects less production of androgen from Leydig cell confirms antiandrogenic nature of the compounds.

Protein :

Significant decreases in the protein contents of testes and reproductive accessories have been shown by administration of the ligand and its complex. Disturbance in the protein synthesis caused by androgen deficiency along with cellular degeneration causes reduction in protein contents in testes. Testicular protein with androgen binding protein (ABP) is important for cellular functions such as stimulation of spermatogonial proliferation, DNA synthesis, increase in the concentration of androgens and binding and delivery of iron in the germ cells. It has been reported that androgen exerts a profound influence on transcription and regulates the synthesis of protein by the provision of more mRNA and functional ribosome³⁷. Administration of antiandrogen compounds causes decrease in protein contents as also found in the present study which reflects antiandrogen nature of compounds. Significant reduction in the protein contents in the present study indicates, decrease androgen supply to accessory organs, observed decrease RNA and protein contents of seminal vesicle after anethole treatment to rats, which is antiandrogenic compound. Similarly in the present study protein contents decreased reflecting antiandrogen nature of the compounds.

Sialic acid :

Sialic acid is a normal constituent of glycoprotein, which in term is an important constituent of the cell membrane, basement membrane and mucin. The most impor-

tant biological function of sialic acid is the functions related to its negative charges, antirecognition properties and macromolecular function as a receptor component. Sialic acid has been detected in reproductive organs of number of mammalian species including the rats, langur monkey. In the present study, the sialic acid contents were decreased after the treatment with the ligands and their complexes, possibly due to the suppression of androgen biosynthesis and secretion, resulting in the lack of testicular function and spermatozoa. Sialic acid whether free or bound to sialonucoprotein, is secreted by the epididymis of humans as well as a number of mammalian species and its level is considered to be androgen dependent. Due to decreased sialic acid, it is likely that the structural integrity of acrosomal membrane of sperm might have altered which ultimately influence their metabolism, motility and fertilizing ability³⁸. Accessory organs like epididymis are known to secrete sialic acid under androgenic control and the reduction in sialic acid contents in epididymis may be due to reduced androgen supply to these organs and decreased number of spermatozoa in lumen.

Histology :

Administration of the ligand and its organogermanium complexes in the different dose levels resulted in the degenerative changes in testes, epididymis, seminal vesicle, vas deferens and ventral prostrate glands.

Testes :

Mammalian testes are divided into seminiferous tubules and vascularized interstitial tissues. Seminiferous tubules are 90% of the total volume of testes. The interstitial space is occupied by Leydig cells blood and lymph vessels and few other cell types with variable amount of connective tissue. Seminiferous tubules show various stages of spermatogenesis. One of the most important cell of tubules are Sertoli cells which provide nutrition and physical support for the developing germ cells. The degenerative changes observed in the testes of ligand and its organogermanium complexes include tubular shrinkage which occurs due to the cell death or sloughing of epithelial cell^{41,42} whereas the sloughing of the microtubule formation in the mitotic apparatus of dividing germ cells are seen which signal doses of the microtubule position. The antiandrogenic effects of the various compounds are reflected in the arrest of the spermatogenesis as seen by

significant reduction in number of spermatocytes, spermatids, sperms and cell debris in the lumen of seminiferous tubules, which may be due to the non availability of the androgens⁴³. The atrophy states of Leydig cells in the testes of the treated rats indicate a reduction of normal LH concentration. Degenerative changes in Leydig cells indicate effect on functional ability of these cells to synthesized testosterone which is required in the maintenance of spermatogenesis⁴⁴. Sertoli cells are the primary supportive cells of the testes creating the necessary structural and physiological environment for germ cells maturation. The process of spermatogenesis is dependent on an orderly sequence of change in Sertoli cell function. Initiation and maintenance of spermatogenesis is under the control of FSH and testosterone, both of which act via the Sertoli cells. The direct effects of the compounds on Sertoli cell function have been shown to produce epithelial disorganization and subsequent tubular atrophy. The treatment with the ligand and its germanium complexes did not cause changes in the number and morphology of Sertoli cells, as the number of Sertoli cells in a tubule remains relatively constant.

Epididymis :

Epididymis play an important role in male reproduction due to the secretory and absorptive properties of its epithelial lining sperm becomes motile and fertile. The epididymis played an integral role in male reproduction by providing a favourable fluid micro environment for sperm maturation and storage. The fluid secreted by the epididymis is controlled by neurotransmitter a substance that is autocrine and paracrine hormones. The physiological and biochemical integrity of epididymis are dependent upon androgen. The cauda epididymis act as sperm storage organ and it has a wider luminal diameter and their epithelial lining than that of the corpus and caput region of epididymis. Epididymal epithelium is sensitive towards androgen and the effects on epididymis possibly due to reduce androgen level and this reflects the antiandrogenic effect of the ligand and its complexes. Deficiency of the androgen caused a marked reduction in tubular diameter, regression of epididymal epithelium, decline in spermatozoa number in cauda epididymis and changes on the composition of epididymis plasma⁴⁴, as observed in the ligand and its complexes treatment which again confirm the antiandrogenic nature of the compounds.

Vas deferens :

Vas deferens plays an important role in sperm transport and seminal emission. The histological aspect of the vas deferens has been widely studied in several mammals including man. The cytological characteristics of the principal cells seem to indicate that these cells are responsible for both the secretory as well as the reproductive functions which are under the control of androgens⁴⁵. The effects of the ligand and its complexes on histoarchitecture of vas deferens with degenerative changes in the epithelium along with the absence of the spermatozoa in the lumen may be due to the reduced androgen levels.

From above observations it can be concluded that the ligands and their organogermanium compounds affect the testes and accessory sex organs without interference in general metabolism. In this way we can say that the synthesized compounds behave as antiandrogenic agents, which arrest spermatogenesis in the testes and reduce sperm production in the epididymis.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to UGC, New Delhi, India for financial support in the form of Grant No. F. 34(324)/08(SR-I).

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